

Classic distance join queries using compact data structures

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Abstract

Distance-based Join Queries (*DJQs*) have multiple applications in spatial databases, Geographic Information Systems, and other areas. The K Closest Pairs Query (*KCPQ*) and the ε Distance Join Query (ε *DJQ*) are well-known *DJQs* that have been widely studied and can be solved using plane-sweep techniques, which are efficient but must keep the whole datasets in main memory. In this work, we propose *DJQ* algorithms that work with data represented using a k^2 -tree, a compact data structure for binary grids. Our algorithms solve *KCPQ* and ε *DJQ* queries, as well as several window-constrained variants, taking advantage of the indexing capabilities of k^2 -trees to efficiently answer queries without the need to decompress the data. Our experimental evaluation with large datasets shows that k^2 -tree algorithms are up to 5 times faster than plane-sweep algorithms in *KCPQ*, and 5–30 times faster in ε *DJQ*. In variants that are window-constrained, our algorithms are competitive in most scenarios and faster for large windows. Additionally, our algorithms are not very affected by the distribution of the data and yield much more predictable query times, showing up to 30 times smaller variance in query times than plane sweep, depending on the location of the query window.

Keywords: k^2 -tree, K Closest Pairs, ε Distance Join, Spatial Query Evaluation

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1. Introduction

The efficient management of increasingly larger spatial datasets has been a very active research topic in the last few decades. In particular, spatial databases have become more common and much more significant in recent years, and a variety of techniques have been developed to handle them. These include, among others, streaming and distributed algorithms, efficient secondary storage management [26], and the use of specialized data structures, such as R-trees or Quadrees, to index the contents and speed up queries [25]. Compression is widely used with spatial data, but classical compression is only useful for archival purposes or for datasets that require simple processing. For example, when only sequential traversals of the entire dataset are performed, compression reduces storage space and speeds up loading time.

Compact data structures [26] store data in compressed (compact) form but provide support for efficient data management without the need to decompress it. In this way, compact data structures combine the low space usage of compressed representations with efficient algorithms to query, navigate, and optionally modify the data in main memory. In many cases, compact data structures can be both smaller and faster than classical representations by exploiting the memory hierarchy (e.g., avoiding expensive disk accesses). The k^2 -tree [8] is a compact data structure that is especially relevant for this work. It was originally designed to manage Web graphs and later used to represent other types of graphs, as well as spatial data [7]. In these scenarios, the k^2 -tree has been shown to efficiently answer relevant queries while requiring less space than most alternatives. The k^2 -tree will be described in detail in Section 3.3.

Distance join queries (DJQs) combine two datasets by taking into account a distance metric. They have received considerable attention from the database community due to their importance in numerous spatial applications, such as geographic information systems (GIS) [31], location-based systems [36], continuous monitoring in streaming systems [43], similarity join of moving object trajectories [13], crime databases [28], road network constrained data management [1, 38], or dynamic cyber-physical-social systems [24], to name but a few. The K Closest Pairs Query (K CPQ) and the ε Distance Join Query (ε DJQ) [11, 12] are two of the most used queries in this family of DJQs. For example, given two point datasets \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{Q} , and a distance function (Euclidean, Manhattan, etc.), K CPQ computes the K pairs of points in $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$ that are closest to each other, while ε DJQ returns all pairs in $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$ that are within a distance ε from each other.

As an example, consider the selection of hotels based on the proximity of free

parking spaces, given two datasets that store hotel locations (\mathcal{P}) and free parking lots (\mathcal{Q}). $KCPQ$ could be used to find the 10 pairs of hotels and free parking lots that have the smallest distance between them. Similarly, εDJQ ($\varepsilon = 300$) would find all possible pairs (hotel, free parking lot) that are within 300 meters of each other.

1.1. Motivation and Challenges

Many contributions on efficient DJQs exist in the literature for input spatial datasets stored on disk, either indexed or not. The most representative contributions in which the datasets are indexed by a spatial access method are based on R-trees [11, 12, 21, 39], quadtrees [23], or xBR^+ -trees [34]. When neither input is indexed and the datasets are stored on disk as a disk array, efficient algorithms based on the plane-sweep method were proposed in [32]. Based on these observations, the use of compact data structures, such as the k^2 -tree, is an exciting and promising option to index spatial datasets in main memory and efficiently perform these DJQs.

Motivated by these facts, in this paper we address the problem of processing DJQs ($KCPQ$ and εDJQ) in main memory using k^2 -trees. To tackle this problem, we propose efficient algorithms to solve these DJQs, taking advantage of the indexing capabilities of the k^2 -tree (a compact data structure based on quadtree space partitioning) and the simplicity of tree traversals, using bitmaps and efficient operations over them. The proposed approaches use novel distance metrics between disjoint matrices to prune k^2 -tree branches during search. The final algorithms achieve faster response times than plane-sweep variants, while also consuming less main memory.

1.2. Contributions and Organization

This paper substantially extends the work we presented in [5]. Its main contributions are the following:

- We provide a more detailed description of the $KCPQ$ and εDJQ algorithms on k^2 -trees, as well as the new metrics used to compute the maximum and minimum possible (euclidean) distances between two matrices that come from the hierarchical decomposition of two k^2 -trees.
- Two new algorithms are presented to solve extensions of $KCPQ$ that restrict the points of one or both datasets to be in a selected rectangular window (Constrained $KCPQ$ and Constrained $KSemiCPQ$).

- The experimental evaluation involving $KCPQ$ and ϵDJQ , which was already present in the preliminary article, has been improved by carefully preprocessing the datasets to better reflect the performance difference among the variants. Furthermore, an existing proposal that implements $KCPQ$ on top of k^2 -trees is experimentally compared with our work.
- A comprehensive experimental evaluation is conducted for the new algorithms to solve Constrained $KCPQ$ and Constrained $KSemiCPQ$. Our experiments analyze the evolution of performance with the relevant parameters of each query, to highlight not only the strengths of our algorithms, but also their scalability and predictability in terms of query times.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we review previous work in the fields of spatial DJQs and the use of k^2 -trees for spatial query processing. Section 3 offers some preliminary concepts and definitions related to DJQs, as well as a detailed description of the compact data structure k^2 -tree. Section 4 describes in detail the new algorithms for $KCPQ$ and ϵDJQ that run over the k^2 -tree representation of the datasets. Section 5 describes two extensions of $KCPQ$ that consider only points in a given query window. In Section 6, we present the results of our experimental evaluation, using large real-world datasets. Finally, in Section 7, we provide some conclusions and discuss directions for future work.

2. Related Work

In this section, we review the most representative contributions in the field of spatial DJQs ($KCPQ$ and ϵDJQ) and describe the use of the k^2 -tree data structure in the context of spatial query processing.

2.1. Spatial DJQs - $KCPQ$ and ϵDJQ

The problem of DJQs has received significant research attention from the spatial database community. Contributions have been proposed in which the input datasets are indexed or not. There are also variants where the query results are required to belong to a specific window, instead of the whole space.

If both datasets are indexed, many contributions have been proposed in the literature, depending on the spatial indexes used (e.g., R-trees [12], Quadtrees [23], bichromatic R-dnn-trees [46], M-trees [15], xBR⁺-trees [34], etc.). When R-trees [20] index both datasets, the concepts of synchronous tree traversal and Depth-First (DF) or Best-First (BF) traversal order can be combined to answer DJQs [12]. In [21], an incremental approach was proposed, allowing results to

be returned one by one according to the distance ordering. In [39], an adaptive multistage algorithm was presented to improve incremental distance joins [21] by including node expansion, sorting dimension, and application of the plane-sweep technique during node pair expansion.

In [46], an extended R-tree (bichromatic R_{dnn}-tree) was proposed by augmenting each non-leaf entry with the maximum nearest neighbor distance (with respect to the other dataset) of points in its subtree. Such distances are utilized during query processing to reduce the search space, outperforming previous R-tree-based methods. A Recursive Best-First Search (RBF) algorithm for DJQs between spatial objects indexed by R-trees was presented in [10], with an exhaustive experimental study that compares DF, BF, and RBF for DJQs, showing that BF is the fastest algorithm. However, BF consumes more memory resources due to the necessary requirements for iterative processing.

In [23], an extensive experimental study was presented, comparing the performance of the R*-tree and Quadtree-like index structures for DJQs (*K*CPQ, *K*NNJQ and *K*-Distance Join query), and their index construction methods. The most representative results show that when the data are static (i.e., when a bulk-loading algorithm is used for the index construction), the R*-tree shows the best performance. However, when the data are dynamic (i.e., frequent updates), a bucket Quadtree outperforms the R*-tree for these DJQs.

DJQs have also been studied on other indexes. For example, [15] proposed efficient algorithms for *K*CPQ in general metric spaces using COM-trees. In [34], algorithms for these DJQs were designed and implemented on xBR⁺-trees, a disk-resident hierarchical pointer-based index structure, built utilizing a regular decomposition of space, optimized for indexing multidimensional points. The most relevant experimental conclusions were that the xBR⁺-trees outperformed R*-trees and R⁺-trees for these DJQs.

When only one data set is indexed, an algorithm was proposed in [19] for *K*CPQ, whose main idea is to partition the space occupied by the non-indexed dataset into several cells or subspaces. This algorithm reduced disk access by 75% with respect to a baseline.

If both datasets are not indexed, the problem of answering *K*CPQ between two sets of points that reside in main memory using plane-sweep algorithms was studied in [33]. As a result, a new algorithm was proposed for *K*CPQ (called *Reverse-Run plane-sweep* (PS-RR) algorithm). PS-RR minimizes the number of distance computations compared to the *Classic plane-sweep* (PS-C) algorithm and it becomes faster. In [32], four plane-sweep-based algorithms were presented for *K*CPQ and their extensions for ϵ DJQ, without using an index on datasets stored

on disk. These algorithms combined plane-sweep [33] and space partitioning techniques (uniform split and uniform filling) to join disk-resident datasets.

Constrained $KCPQ$ ($KCCPQ$) has been extensively studied in the literature, and the most representative contributions are [12, 29, 37, 27]. In [29], the Range $KCPQ$ ($KRCPQ$) is examined as an extension of $KCPQ$, which requires the query results to be located within a given region. The authors proposed an efficient $KRCPQ$ algorithm based on a query window and used a density-based range estimation method to approximate the circle query range. In [37], the authors suggested a practical extension of the closest pair problem to involve a query range, assuming that $\mathcal{P} = \mathcal{Q}$ and the dataset is indexed by an R-tree. The proposed method augments the R-tree nodes with auxiliary information concerning the closest pair of objects that resides in each tree branch, and this information is adjusted accordingly during insertions and deletions.

In [27], the Constrained $KSemiCPQ$ ($KCSCPQ$) was introduced as an extension of $KCPQ$. The $KSemiCPQ$ reports K pairs of objects (p, q) with $p \in \mathcal{P}$ and $q \in \mathcal{Q}$ having the smallest distances between them and presents the constraint that each object p appears at most once in the final result. In $KCSCPQ$, an additional spatial constraint is applied, requiring that each object $p \in \mathcal{P}$ that appears in the final result must be enclosed by a spatial region R (query window). Several algorithms were presented and evaluated using real-life and synthetic datasets.

2.2. Spatial query processing with k^2 -trees

The k^2 -tree [8] is a compact data structure originally designed to represent Web graphs. Essentially, a k^2 -tree is a succinct quadtree representation that supports the basic traversal operations in very reduced space. Section 3.3 presents a comprehensive explanation of the k^2 -tree data structure and the operations it supports.

Several variants of the k^2 -tree have been applied to the representation of spatial data. Most of these focus on the representation of raster data [7]. Other works have proposed join operations involving basic set operations on k^2 -trees [30], as well as spatial join operations between raster data stored in k^2 -trees and vectorial data stored in R-trees [6].

Regarding the use of k^2 -trees in the field of DJQs, a recent work presented in [35] proposes practical algorithms for the resolution of $KCPQ$, as well as KNN . Their $KCPQ$ algorithm (ALBA- $KCPQ$) is, to our knowledge, the first solution that uses k^2 -trees. Their theoretical proposal is based on a synchronized traversal of two k^2 -trees and is similar to ours. However, we consider that their results are questionable. They work with relatively small datasets, in terms of the number of

points and spatial resolution. Even for these small datasets, their baseline (Classic) plane-sweep-based *KCPQ* algorithm requires about an hour to solve most *KCPQ* queries when our results suggest that most queries should be answered in a few seconds. Regrettably, their implementation is not able to load our larger datasets, so only a limited comparison with their proposal has been conducted. We will discuss the characteristics of their implementation and its limitations in Section 6.

To our knowledge, other variants of DJQ, such as ε DJQ, *KCCPQ*, or *KCSCPQ*, have never been tackled using k^2 -trees. In this work, we present efficient implementations of *KCPQ* and ε DJQ, as well as extensions to solve *KRCPQ* and *KCSCPQ*. Our algorithms were coded in C++ and are available to the community¹. They were tested with large real-world datasets and compared with *Classic* and *Reverse-Run* plane-sweep DJQs in main memory.

2.3. Summary and Recent Contributions

Table 1 synthesizes the most relevant contributions for *KCPQ* depending on whether the datasets involved in the query are indexed or not, and extensions of this join-based query where R-trees index both datasets. Other interesting *KCPQ* variants have also been well studied in the literature [9], such as self-*KCP* queries [12, 27], *KCPQ* on moving objects [48], exclusive *KCP* retrieval [43], top-*K* set similarity join [45], *KCPQ* in high-dimensional spaces [41], and *KCPQ* on spatial networks [1], to name but a few.

Table 1: *KCPQ* depending on the indexing of datasets and the most representative extensions.

<i>K</i> Closest Pairs Query - <i>KCPQ</i>		
Both datasets indexed	One dataset indexed	No datasets indexed
R-trees [12, 10] [21, 39]	R-tree + VA-File-based partitioning (VR-BCP) [19]	Classic PS [33, 32]
Quadtrees [23]		Reverse-Run PS [32]
COM-trees [15]		
xBR ⁺ -trees [34]		
Rdm-trees [46]		
k^2 -trees [35, 5]		
Extensions of <i>KCPQ</i> where both datasets are indexed by R-trees		
ε DJQ [10], Constrained <i>KCPQ</i> [12, 37, 27, 29], Constrained <i>KSemiCPQ</i> [27]		

In addition to all of the above, [47] and [3] have recently investigated the

¹Available at <https://gitlab.lbd.org.es/public-sources/djq/k2tree-djq>

solution of *KCPQ* in high-dimensional spaces using LSH-based algorithms. In particular, [47] proposed PM-LSH to index the projected points directly using the PM-tree (metric index based on M-tree) without applying the Z-order, and in [3], an extension of the LSH forest approach is used to solve *KCPQ* in high-dimensional data. Additionally, in [2], LSH-based similarity join (ϵ DJQ) algorithms were presented for high-dimensional data spaces. Furthermore, *KCPQ* has also been studied in distributed spatial data management systems based on Hadoop [17] and Spark [18, 16]. More precisely, an efficient *KCPQ* MapReduce algorithm was proposed for SpatialHadoop in [17]. In [18], a distributed algorithm *KCPQ* was designed and implemented for LocationSpark and compared with the MapReduce algorithm in SpatialHadoop. In [16], distributed *KCPQ* algorithms are implemented and compared in Spark-based spatial analytics systems (Simba, LocationSpark, and Apache Sedona). Another interesting contribution is proposed in [40], a simple and efficient algorithm for the closest pair problem, using pre-processing based on exponent bucketing and exponent windowing respecting the accuracy of the floating-point representation. Finally, the closest pairs search has also been examined lately on data streams [49] and spatial knowledge graphs [44], highlighting the excellent research activity on this topic in recent years.

3. Preliminaries and Background

In this section, we first present the basic definitions of the DJQs (*KCPQ* and ϵ DJQ) studied in this paper. Next, algorithms based on the plane-sweep technique are described for processing *KCPQ* and ϵ DJQ in main memory. Finally, the k^2 -tree compact data structure and its basic traversal algorithms are also reviewed.

3.1. Distance-based Join Queries - *KCPQ* and ϵ DJQ

Distance-based Join Queries are special joins where two datasets are combined, taking into account a distance metric (*dist*). DJQs can be very costly when the size of the joined datasets is large, so they have been thoroughly investigated lately. Two of the most representative and known DJQs are the *K* Closest Pairs Query (*KCPQ*) and the ϵ Distance Join Query (ϵ DJQ).

The *KCPQ* discovers the *K* pairs of data formed from the elements of two datasets with the *K* smallest distances between them (that is, it reports only the top *K* pairs from the combination of two datasets). Formally:

Definition 1. *K Closest Pairs query, KCPQ* Let $\mathcal{P} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\}$ and $\mathcal{Q} = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_m\}$ be two set of points, and a number $K \in \mathbb{N}^+$. Then, the result of

the K Closest Pairs Query is an ordered collection, $KCPQ(\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{Q}, K)$, containing K different pairs of points from $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$, ordered by distance, with the K smallest distances between all possible pairs:

$KCPQ(\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{Q}, K) = ((p_1, q_1), (p_2, q_2), \dots, (p_K, q_K)), (p_i, q_i) \in \mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}, 1 \leq i \leq K$, such that for any $(p, q) \in \mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q} \setminus KCPQ(\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{Q}, K)$ we have $dist(p_1, q_1) \leq dist(p_2, q_2) \leq \dots \leq dist(p_K, q_K) \leq dist(p, q)$.

On the other hand, εDJQ reports all the possible pairs of spatial objects from two different spatial object datasets, \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{Q} , with a distance between them not greater than a threshold ε . Formally:

Definition 2. ε *Distance Join Query*, εDJQ Let $\mathcal{P} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\}$ and $\mathcal{Q} = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_m\}$ be two sets of points, and a distance threshold $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. Then, the result of the εDJQ is the set, $\varepsilon DJQ(\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{Q}, \varepsilon) \subseteq \mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$, containing all possible different pairs of points from $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$ that have a distance from each other smaller than or equal to ε :

$$\varepsilon DJQ(\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{Q}, \varepsilon) = \{(p_i, q_j) \in \mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q} : dist(p_i, q_j) \leq \varepsilon\}$$

The εDJQ can be considered as an extension of the $KCPQ$, where the distance threshold of the pairs (ε) is known in advance, and the processing strategy (for example, the plane sweep technique) can be the same as in the $KCPQ$ to generate the candidate pairs of the final result.

3.2. $DJQs$ using the plane-sweep technique

Plane-sweep is one of the most important paradigms for designing geometric algorithms [4]. The *plane-sweep* (or sweep-line) technique is widely used in computational geometry (e.g., line segment intersections, Voronoi Diagrams, Convex Hull, triangulation, etc.) in the context of spatial databases [31]. This technique consists of decomposing the geometric input into vertical strips, such that the relevant information to the problem to solve is located on the vertical lines that separate the two strips. Therefore, by *sweeping* a vertical line from left to right, stopping at the boundaries of the strips, we can maintain and update the information needed to solve a given problem [31]. The plane-sweep technique has been successfully used in spatial databases to report the result of several well-known spatial queries (e.g., $KNNQ$, spatial join, $KCPQ$, Skyline Query, etc.), regardless of whether the sets of spatial objects are indexed or not.

In the context of $DJQs$, the plane-sweep technique has been successfully used to improve the brute-force nested loop algorithm (where all possible combinations

Figure 1: A 2D-space model with its binary matrix and k^2 -tree representations.

of pairs of points should be tested) by significantly reducing the number of distance computations and making the plane-sweep-based DJQ algorithm much faster [12, 39, 33, 32]. If both datasets \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{Q} are non-indexed, K CPQ between two set of points that reside in main memory can be solved by the *Classic* and *Reverse-Run* plane-sweep algorithms [33, 32]. Additionally, to reduce the search space even more during query processing, three improvements on both plane-sweep-based algorithms for K CPQ are presented in [33, 32]: (1) *Sliding Strip*, (2) *Sliding Window*, and (3) *Sliding Semi-Circle*.

The adaptation of the plane-sweep-based algorithms from K CPQ to ε DJQ is straightforward and can be found in [32]. In general, if we have two sorted sets (arrays) of points, we only select those pairs of points with distances less than or equal to ε for the final result. That is, the pruning distance is always ε (distance threshold) instead of the distance value of the K^{th} closest pair found so far.

3.3. k^2 -tree

The k^2 -tree [8] is a compact data structure designed to store and query a binary matrix. As explained in Section 2.2, it has been used in the past to efficiently store and query spatial data following a raster representation of the space. Given its relevance to our work, we describe in this section the main components of the k^2 -tree data structure and the basic algorithms to perform queries on k^2 -trees, focusing on its application to spatial data.

Figure 1 shows a set of points mapped into a discrete 2D grid (a) and the corresponding binary matrix (b). In the following description, we assume that we are representing a collection of points in the space, although this can be generalized to any binary matrix.

The conceptual k^2 -tree is built by recursively partitioning the space into equal-sized regions. A parameter k is used to guide the partition of the space, so the space is divided into $k \times k$ equal-sized subregions at each step. In fact, for the typical value $k = 2$, the k^2 -tree can be regarded as a succinct representation of the classical MX-quadtrees.

The root of the tree corresponds to the first partition of the space into $k \times k$ regions. Each region is represented using a single bit that is set to 1 if the region contains at least one point and set to 0 if the region contains no points. The example in Figure 1 displays in (c) the conceptual tree for the collection of points in (a). In this example, we use $k = 2$, so the space is partitioned into quadrants (always traversed in the usual order NW-NE-SW-SE). Therefore, the root node in (c) contains 4 bits, and only the fourth bit (SE quadrant) is set to zero because that is the only quadrant with no points. The partitioning process continues recursively for all regions that contain at least one point. Each of these regions will generate a child of the current node and will be decomposed again into $k \times k$ subregions. The decomposition eventually stops when the cells in the original matrix are reached. Note that all the points in the collection are represented by a 1 in some leaf of the conceptual tree and that all the leaves are at the same level.

Navigation of the conceptual tree is straightforward, given the fixed partition of the space. For instance, to retrieve the value of a specific cell of the matrix (i.e., identifying if the cell contains or not a point), we start at the root node and identify the subregion where the point would fall. If the corresponding bit is a 0, we stop the traversal immediately, since there are no points in the given region. If the corresponding bit is a 1, we navigate to the corresponding child and repeat the check in the associated subregion. Retrieval of all the points in a given region requires a traversal of all the nodes of the tree that overlap the region.

The actual data structure k^2 -tree is a succinct representation of the conceptual tree. The bits of all internal nodes are read following a breadth-first traversal of the tree and stored in a single bit sequence T . The leaf nodes are also combined in a second bit sequence L . Figure 1(d) displays the bit sequences obtained for the conceptual tree in (c).

All navigation algorithms can be efficiently performed in practice using only bitmaps T and L . Navigation always starts at the root node, which is located in $T[0 \dots k^2 - 1]$. Given a bit at position i in T , such that $T[i] = 1$, we define a *getChild* operation that returns the starting position of the corresponding child node. The key observation to implement this operation is the following: each bit set to 1 is a subregion that is recursively traversed, so each 1 generates k^2 bits in the next level, and bits set to 0 have no effect in lower levels. Given that T stores

all bits in breadth-first order, we can compute $getChild(T, i) = rank_1(T, i) \times k^2$, where $rank_1(T, i)$ returns the number of bits set to 1 in the bit sequence T from the beginning up to position i . When we reach the last level of the conceptual tree, we get $i' = getChild(T, i) > |T|$ and we access the child at $L[i' - |T|]$ instead. The $rank_1$ operation has been widely studied, and theoretical and practical solutions have been proposed to compute it in constant time by enhancing the bit sequence with a *rank structure* storing partial counters. This structure requires additional sublinear space [22]. With this *rank structure*, the parent-child navigation in the tree can be solved in constant time, using only the space needed by T and L (plus the sublinear rank structure that is only necessary on T).

The basic k^2 -tree described in this section has been enhanced by variants that aim at improving compression and query times [8]. Hybrid k^2 -trees can use different values of k at different levels of the conceptual tree, taking advantage of higher values of k at the upper levels of the tree to improve query times, without increasing the space required (or even slightly reducing it). Other variants improve compression by effectively stopping decomposition on matrices of size $k' \times k'$ and storing the sequence of submatrices separately using statistical compression to reduce their size.

Specific variants of the k^2 -tree have also been proposed to represent raster data [7]. These variants aim at improving compression significantly when the grid contains not isolated points but large connected regions (e.g. when representing cloud coverage or oil spills). The simplest of these solutions adds a bitmap T' to label the 0s of T , so that a 0 in T can represent either empty regions (regions of 0s) or fully covered regions (regions of 1s). These variants can be regarded as a succinct representation of classical region quadtrees.

4. Our approach to DJQs using k^2 -trees

We describe in this section the new algorithms for KCPQ and ϵ DJQ using k^2 -trees. The algorithm for KCPQ is explained in Section 4.2 and detailed in Algorithm 2. The algorithm for ϵ DJQ is explained in Section 4.3 and is detailed in Algorithm 3. The main variables and parameters used in these algorithms are summarized in Table 2.

A fundamental measure for these algorithms is, of course, the distance. We use the Euclidean distance between points, but as we will show, we also have to consider the minimum and maximum possible distances between points in two matrices, and we have devised new, slightly optimized algorithms to compute those distances.

Table 2: Summary of variables and parameters used.

Variable	Description
$\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$	Set of points $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$
p_i, q_j	i -th point in \mathcal{P} (j -th point in \mathcal{Q})
K	Number of points to be retrieved in a K CPQ query
ε	Threshold for ε DJQ: only pairs with a distance $\leq \varepsilon$ are considered
$A(B)$	Matrix storing a set of points $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$ in a discrete grid
$MinMinDist(A,B)$	Minimum possible distance between pairs $(a,b), a \in A, b \in B$
$MaxMaxDist(A,B)$	Maximum possible distance between pairs $(a,b), a \in A, b \in B$
T, L	Bit sequences that compose the k^2 -tree
k	Parameter that guides decomposition in the k^2 -tree. In this work $k = 2$
$P(\mathcal{Q})$	k^2 -tree storing the set of points $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$
$MinDist(A, B, size)$	Computes $MinMinDist(A, B)$ for k^2 -tree submatrices of size $size$
$MaxDist(A, B, size)$	Computes $MaxMaxDist(A, B)$ for k^2 -tree submatrices of size $size$

4.1. Computing distances

The minimum possible distance was defined in [11] as $MinMinDist(A, B)$, where A and B are matrices (actually, MBRs or Minimum Bounding Rectangles enclosing sets of points). Similarly, the maximum possible distance was defined as $MaxMaxDist(A, B)$. Both can be seen in Figure 2(a).

We chose not to use those two distances in our work and implemented an optimized version of them, because of the nature of the matrices generated by our algorithms. These matrices, which follow the natural recursive decomposition of k^2 -trees, never overlap in any of the two dimensions. Thus, the minimum possible distance can always be calculated as the distance between two vertices of the matrices (see Figure 2(b)), unlike the generic $MinMinDist$, which can also be the distance between a vertex and a segment (Figure 2(a)). Also, note that $MinDist$ is 1 for two adjacent matrices and $\sqrt{2}$ when the matrices seem to touch each other in one corner. It would seem that this distance is 0 because they share a segment or a point, but that is not the case. The k^2 -tree discretizes the space, so the coordinates are integers and not floating-point numbers, and the k^2 -tree partitions are always disjoint.

Considering a matrix A that comes from the partitioning of a k^2 -tree, it can be defined by its top-left coordinate, which we will name A_0 and the $size$ of the matrix. Following this notation, we can describe our optimized version of the functions $MinDist(A_0, B_0, size)$ and $MaxDist(A_0, B_0, size)$ to compute the minimum and maximum possible distance between two matrices. The pseudocode for both is shown in Algorithm 1. Note that, although our functions are optimized, they are specific for matrices that come from the k^2 -tree decomposition and would

Figure 2: Min and Max distances between matrices.

not work for two matrices (or MBRs) in general.

Algorithm 1 Minimum and maximum possible distance between the points of 2 matrices that come from the decomposition of a k^2 -tree.

```

1: function MINDIST( $A_0, B_0, size$ )
2:    $\triangleright$  Also MAXDIST( $A_0, B_0, size$ )
3:   if  $A_0.x = B_0.x$  then
4:      $hdist = 0$ 
5:   else
6:      $hdist = |A_0.x - B_0.x| - (size - 1)$ 
7:      $\triangleright$  For MaxDist:  $hdist = |A_0.x - B_0.x| + (size - 1)$ 
8:   if  $A_0.y = B_0.y$  then
9:      $vdist = 0$ 
10:  else
11:     $vdist = |A_0.y - B_0.y| - (size - 1)$ 
12:     $\triangleright$  For MaxDist:  $vdist = |A_0.y - B_0.y| + (size - 1)$ 
13:  return  $\sqrt{hdist^2 + vdist^2}$ 

```

4.2. KCPQ Algorithm

KCPQ takes as input two k^2 -trees P and Q (they store the matrices that correspond to the datasets \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{Q} used in the definitions in Section 3.1) and the number K of pairs of closest points (note the use of uppercase K to represent the number of pairs the algorithm must obtain, not to be confused with lowercase k , the parameter of k^2 -trees). We denote by $P[i]$ the i^{th} bit value of the bitmap for P . $P.lastLevel$ is the last level of the tree, corresponding to its leaves. The levels range from 0 to $\lceil \lg(n) \rceil - 1$, being n the width of the original matrix.

The following data structures are used by KCPQ (its pseudocode is shown in Algorithm 2):

- A Priority Queue *PQueue* that stores pairs of nodes to be processed. It was implemented as a min-heap over the distance between the nodes, with the minimum distance located on the top element. It uses standard methods for priority queues: *isEmpty()*, *enqueue()*, and *dequeue()*. Each entry in *PQueue* contains:
 - *P*: it is either the whole input matrix for the k^2 -tree that stores the \mathcal{P} dataset, or any submatrix following the k^2 -tree partitioning. It is defined by its origin coordinates (x, y) , and also includes the offset of the corresponding node in the k^2 -tree bitmap (which is the concatenation of T and L , represented as $T|L$).
 - *Q*: Contains the same information for the matrix represented by the k^2 -tree that stores the \mathcal{Q} dataset.
 - The level where *P* and *Q* stand in the k^2 -tree conceptual trees. Note that both matrices are always at the same level; they are square and each matrix is fully described by the point that represents its top-left coordinate and its size, which can be computed as n/k^{level} .
 - The minimum possible distance between *P* and *Q*. It is calculated as shown in Algorithm 1.
- A max-heap *OutList* to store the current candidate pairs of points for the solution. It has the capacity to contain K elements, each being a pair of points (from *P* and *Q*) and the distance between them. The top of this heap contains the pair with the highest distance between its points. It is managed using the methods *length()* (number of elements), *maxDist()* (the distance stored on the top element of the heap), and *insert()*. This last method inserts a new element into the heap, but only if its distance is lower than the current *maxDist()*. Additionally, if the heap was already full (containing K elements), the current top element is removed from the heap.

KCPQ follows a Best-First (BF) approach to recursively partition and compare *P* and *Q* search for candidate pairs. In each step, *P* and *Q* are split into (up to) k^2 submatrices, and all combinations are compared, computing the minimum possible distance between them. Each pair capable of producing candidate pairs is enqueued in the priority queue. At the last level, the matrices are just points. In this case, the real distance between them is calculated, and the candidate pairs are inserted into the output list. One of the aspects that can make this algorithm fast is that it can stop without having to process all pairs of submatrices. If the candidate

output list already has all the K needed pairs and the maximum distance so far is not greater than the minimum distance in the priority queue, we can be sure that the queue will not produce any candidate pairs. In this case, the algorithm can return the current candidate list.

Let us show the algorithm in more detail, following the pseudocode of Algorithm 2. The first step (initialization) is to enqueue the root nodes of the k^2 -trees, which represent the whole P and Q matrices, with a minimum possible distance of 0. *OutList* is also initialized as an empty max-heap with a capacity for K elements.

Then, the priority queue is processed in a loop.

In each step of the loop, the top element of the priority queue is dequeued to obtain two matrices, P and Q , which are partitioned (lines 11 – 20) into up to k^2 submatrices. Only nonempty submatrices are considered (which is tested by directly using the k^2 -tree bitmaps in lines 13 for matrix P and 15 for matrix Q).

If the pair of submatrices is actually a pair of points (they correspond to the last level of the k^2 -trees), that pair can be a candidate pair for the solution. If *OutList* currently has less than K elements, or the distance between the points is less than the current *OutList.maxDist()*, then the pair is inserted into *OutList* (lines 20-24). Recall that the *insert* operation deletes the current top element (which has the largest distance) if *OutList* already has K elements. If the pair of submatrices is not at the last level of the k^2 -trees and can contain candidate pairs of points (*OutList* does not yet have K elements or the minimum distance between the matrices is less than *OutList.maxDist()*), then they are enqueued in the priority queue (lines 29-32).

The algorithm stops either when the queue is empty or when we have a valid answer, which is checked in lines 8-9. If *OutList* already has K elements and the minimum possible distance between the pair of matrices being processed is not less than *OutList.maxDist()*, we can return *OutList* because no better candidate pairs will be produced from the current pair or those in the priority queue (recall that it is a minimum priority queue).

4.3. ε DJQ algorithm

ε DJQ uses a similar approach to KCPQ, partitioning and measuring the distances between the submatrices.

Besides P and Q , the input now includes the distance threshold ε instead of the K desired pairs of KCPQ. Given that the number of output pairs is not limited and the comparison of distances between pairs is not relevant (only with ε), *OutList* is now an unordered list of unlimited capacity. The same motives force this algorithm

Algorithm 2 KCPQ: Get the K closest pairs of points.

```
1: function KCPQ(P, Q, K)
2:    $rootP \leftarrow \{point : (x : 0, y : 0), ptr : 0\}$ 
3:    $rootQ \leftarrow \{point : (x : 0, y : 0), ptr : 0\}$ 
4:    $PQueue.enqueue(\{P : rootP, Q : rootQ, level : 0, minDist : 0\})$ 
5:    $OutList \leftarrow newOrderedList(K)$ 
6:   while not  $PQueue.isEmpty()$  do
7:      $Node \leftarrow PQueue.dequeue()$ 
8:     if  $OutList.length() == K$  and  $Node.minDist \geq OutList.maxDist()$  then
9:       return  $OutList$ 
10:     $chLevel \leftarrow Node.Level + 1$ 
11:     $chSize \leftarrow n/k^{chLevel}$ 
12:    for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $k^2 - 1$  do
13:      if  $P[Node.P.ptr + i] == 1$  then
14:        for  $j \leftarrow 0$  to  $k^2 - 1$  do
15:          if  $Q[Node.Q.ptr + j] == 1$  then
16:             $childP \leftarrow \{point : (x : Node.P.point.x + chSize \cdot (i \bmod k),$ 
17:               $y : Node.P.point.y + chSize \cdot \lfloor i/k \rfloor), ptr : 0\}$ 
18:             $childQ = \{point : (x : Node.Q.point.x + chSize \cdot (j \bmod k),$ 
19:               $y : Node.Q.point.y + chSize \cdot \lfloor j/k \rfloor), ptr : 0\}$ 
20:            if  $chLevel == P.lastLevel$  then ▷ Leaf nodes
21:               $distance = Dist(childP.point, childQ.point)$ 
22:              if  $OutList.length() < K$ 
23:                or  $OutList.maxDist() > distance$  then
24:                 $OutList.insert(childP.point, childQ.point, distance)$ 
25:            else
26:               $childP.ptr \leftarrow getChild(P, Node.P.ptr + i)$ 
27:               $childQ.ptr \leftarrow getChild(Q, Node.Q.ptr + j)$ 
28:               $min\_dist \leftarrow MinDist(childP.point, childQ.point, chSize)$ 
29:              if  $OutList.length() < K$ 
30:                or  $OutList.maxDist() > minDist$  then
31:                 $PQueue.enqueue(\{P : childP, Q : childQ,$ 
32:                   $level : chLevel, minDist : min\_dist\})$ 
33:   return  $OutList$ 
```

to process the queue until it is empty. This algorithm does not have an early exit condition (like *KCPQ*), but it can directly discard many pairs of submatrices if the minimum distance between them is greater than ε . For ε DJQ, we also need to store the maximum possible distance between each pair of submatrices in the priority queue elements (computed by the function *MaxDist*, commented out in Algorithm 1), along with *P*, *Q* and its *MinDist*. When the initialization step takes place, enqueueing the whole *P* and *Q*, *MaxDist* is $\sqrt{2}n$, being *n* the width of the entire matrix.

When processing each pair of submatrices, the following actions are performed:

- In non-leaf levels of the k^2 -trees, if the maximum possible distance *MaxDist* between the two submatrices is not greater than ε , then all the combinations of points are within the desired range. Therefore, we get all these combinations of points (the k^2 -tree *rangeQuery* operation is used to get the points belonging to the submatrices) and insert them, along with their distance, into *OutList* (lines 27-35).

Otherwise, if the minimum distance between the pair of matrices is larger than ε , the pair is discarded (not enqueued). This step can significantly decrease the number of pairs of matrices to be processed.

Finally, if the minimum possible distance between the matrices is not larger than ε , the submatrices are enqueued, along with their minimum and maximum distances (lines 36-38).

- If the submatrices are points (they correspond to the last level of the k^2 -trees), the pair of nodes is inserted into *OutList* if the distance between them is at most ε (lines 18-21). Note that, in this case, no element is ever removed from *OutList*.

5. Extensions of *KCPQ* constrained to window range

In this section, we describe our algorithms for two extensions of *KCPQ* in which the resulting points are constrained to be in a specified rectangular window. The first, *KWCPQ*, simply forces the points of one or both datasets to be in the window, and the second, *KWCSCPQ*, additionally requires that each point of the first dataset appears at most once in the result.

To show the usefulness of these operations in the real world, we reuse the example from the Introduction 1. Consider the pairs of hotels and free parking

Algorithm 3 ε DJQ: Get all pairs with a distance threshold of ε .

```
1: function  $\varepsilon$ DJQ( $P, Q, \varepsilon$ )
2:    $rootP \leftarrow \{point : (x : 0, y : 0), ptr : 0\}$ 
3:    $rootQ \leftarrow \{point : (x : 0, y : 0), ptr : 0\}$ 
4:    $PQueue.enqueue(\{P : rootP, Q : rootQ, level : 0, minDist : 0, maxDist : \sqrt{2n}\})$ 
5:    $OutList \leftarrow newList()$ 
6:   while not  $PQueue.isEmpty()$  do
7:      $Node \leftarrow PQueue.dequeue()$ 
8:      $chLevel \leftarrow Node.Level + 1$ 
9:      $chSize \leftarrow n/k^{chLevel}$ 
10:    for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $k^2 - 1$  do
11:      if  $P[Node.P.ptr + i] == 1$  then
12:        for  $j \leftarrow 0$  to  $k^2 - 1$  do
13:          if  $Q[Node.Q.ptr + j] == 1$  then
14:             $childP = \{point : (x : Node.P.x + chSize \cdot (i \bmod k),$ 
15:               $y : Node.P.y + chSize \cdot \lfloor i/k \rfloor), ptr : 0\}$ 
16:             $childQ = \{point : (x : Node.Q.x + chSize \cdot (j \bmod k),$ 
17:               $y : Node.Q.y + chSize \cdot \lfloor j/k \rfloor), ptr : 0\}$ 
18:            if  $chLevel == P.lastLevel$  then ▷ Leaf nodes
19:               $distance = Dist(childP.point, childQ.point)$ 
20:              if  $distance \leq \varepsilon$  then
21:                 $OutList.insert(childP.point, childQ.point, distance)$ 
22:            else
23:               $childP.ptr \leftarrow getChild(P, Node.P.ptr + i)$ 
24:               $childQ.ptr \leftarrow getChild(Q, Node.Q.ptr + j)$ 
25:               $min\_dist = MinDist(childP.point, childQ.point, chSize)$ 
26:               $max\_dist = MaxDist(childP.point, childQ.point, chSize)$ 
27:              if  $max\_dist \leq \varepsilon$  then
28:                ▷ All pairs in the range satisfy the distance condition
29:                 $rangeP \leftarrow P.rangeQuery(childP.point.x,$ 
30:                   $childP.point.x + chSize - 1, childP.point.y, childP.point.y + chSize - 1)$ 
31:                 $rangeQ \leftarrow Q.rangeQuery(childQ.point.x,$ 
32:                   $childQ.point.x + chSize - 1, childQ.point.y, childQ.point.y + chSize - 1)$ 
33:                for  $pointP \in rangeP$  do
34:                  for  $pointQ \in rangeQ$  do
35:                     $OutList.insert(pointP, pointQ, Dist(pointP, pointQ))$ 
36:                else if  $minDist \leq \varepsilon$  then
37:                   $PQueue.enqueue(\{P : childP, Q : childQ, level : chLevel,$ 
38:                     $minDist : min\_dist, maxDist : max\_dist\})$ 
39:   return  $OutList$ 
```

lots in a city, and let us see how the window constraints would work. If we want to consider hotels in a given area (the query window), we might be interested in nearby parking lots even if they are not inside the area, so only hotels should be constrained. If we consider parking lots in a given area, we might want to locate nearby hotels even outside of it, so only parking lots should be constrained. For a combination of both, the two datasets should be restricted to the query window. Additionally, it might make sense to restrict the result of the query to hotels in a given area and offer only one parking lot suggestion for each hotel (the closest one).

The following subsections will describe the extended algorithms in more detail. The specification of the query windows for *KWCPQ* was relatively straightforward for both k^2 -trees and the plane-sweep techniques. However, the extension of the algorithm was more complex for *KWSCPQ*. It required using an additional data structure, namely, a hash table, to enforce the constraint that any point of the first dataset must appear only once in the result.

5.1. *KCPQ* constrained to a query window - *KWCPQ*

We use *KWCPQ* (*K* Window Closest Points Query) for the same query called *Range-CP* in [37], just to stress that the ranges we are dealing with are rectangular windows. We define $KWCPQ(P, Q, K, W)$, where W is the query window, as the result of $KCPQ(P, Q, K)$ when only the points of P and Q that are inside W are considered. In fact, we can obtain three variants of this definition, depending on whether only the points in P , only the points in Q , or both are required to be in W . The first variant will be named *KWCPQ-First* in the experimental evaluation section.

Extending the previous k^2 -tree-based algorithms to consider only the points belonging to a window is straightforward; simply test if a submatrix intersects the window (or, if it is a point, if it is inside the window) before considering it. The test itself is implemented as the *inWindow* function shown in Algorithm 4, where the matrix A is defined by its top-left corner A_0 and its *size* (the side length of the square). It works for both matrices and points (when *size* is equal to 1).

Algorithm 4 *inWindow*: Test whether a matrix intersects a rectangular window.

```

1: function inWindow( $A_0, size, win$ )
2:   return ( $win.x1 \leq A_0.x + (size - 1)$ ) and ( $win.x2 \geq A_0.x$ ) and ( $win.y1 \leq A_0.y + (size - 1)$ ) and ( $win.y2 \geq A_0.y$ )

```

These tests must be added in lines 13 and 15 for *KCPQ* (Algorithm 2) to check if *childP* and *childQ* intersect the window (thus, *childP* and *childQ* must be

calculated before). For ε DJQ (Algorithm 3), the test must be included in lines 11 and 13. Of course, considering the three defined variants, only the relevant checks should be included.

To adapt the *KCPQ* plane-sweep algorithms (Classic and Reverse-Run) to the definition of *KWCPQ*, we have to use the *range query followed by plane-sweep* technique proposed in [37]. It consists of two steps: (1) performing a window query on each dataset to get only the points inside the query window, and then (2) performing the *KCPQ* plane-sweep algorithms on these restricted subsets. In this way, we guarantee that the points in all pairs of the result set ($KCPQ(\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{Q}, K)$) are inside the query window W . Variations in which the query window constraint only applies to one dataset are solved by following the same approach.

5.2. *K-SemiCPQ* constrained to a query window *KWSCPQ*

KWSCPQ (*K* Window Semi-Closest Points Query) reports the *K* closest pairs of points between two datasets, with two conditions for the points from the first dataset: (1) they are required to be in the query window, and (2) each one of them may appear at most once in the result. This query roughly corresponds to *KCSCPQ*, as defined in [27], but again, we stress the fact that the query constraining the points is a rectangular window.

To adapt the k^2 -tree-based *KCPQ* Algorithm to *KWSCPQ*, we take care of the two previous conditions. The query window constraint is handled as in *KWCPQ*. For the second condition, we enforce that each point of the first dataset appears only once in the output list. This restriction is achieved by modifying how pairs are inserted. The pair is inserted as usual if the first point is not in the output list. However, if the first point is already in the list, we must check the associated distances. If the new pair has a distance lower than the current one, then the new pair replaces the current one in the list; otherwise, it is discarded. As an implementation detail, to speed up the required tests, a hash table (with the first point as the key and the current lowest distance as the value) was associated with the output list. The implementation of ε DJQ (Algorithm 3) follows the same approach.

To adapt the *KCPQ* plane-sweep algorithms (Classic and Reverse-Run) to answer *KWSCPQ*, in addition to keeping the heap to store the *K* closest pairs (with the condition that the first member of each pair appears at most once), we also need to maintain a *hash table* with the *hash function* proposed in [42] and adapted to the 2D space. This hash table stores the current minimum distance for each pair inside the max-heap and is associated with it for fast searching and updating during query processing. Similarly to *KWCPQ*, we have to use the

range query followed by plane-sweep technique [37]. First, we restrict the query processing only to the points of the first dataset that are inside the window W by performing a window query. Next, we also constrain the second dataset to points inside a window W' , which expands the original query window W in all directions, in order to keep all the points from this dataset that could be candidates for the final result of the query. Horizontally, the window is expanded to include K extra points to the left and right. Let $\delta_{K_{XL}}$ be the extension to the left and $\delta_{K_{XR}}$ the extension to the right. Vertically, we extend the window at both ends by the maximum of the previous distances ($\delta_{K_{YU}} = \delta_{K_{YD}} = \max\{\delta_{K_{XL}}, \delta_{K_{XR}}\}$). Now, we are ready to perform a plane-sweep algorithm (Classic or Reverse-Run). The combined hash table and the max-heap store the K pairs and ensure that the first member of the pair appears at most once in the result.

6. Experimental Results

In this section, we experimentally evaluate the performance of the k^2 -tree-based algorithms for DJQs. Section 6.1 describes the datasets and the general methodology for the experiments. Section 6.2 analyzes the compression capabilities of the k^2 -trees. Section 6.3 includes a limited comparison with existing alternatives based on k^2 -trees. The remaining sections focus on the query performance of the k^2 -tree algorithms, comparing them with the plane-sweep variants described above. Section 6.4 shows the results obtained in K CPQ and ϵ DJQ. Section 6.5 focuses on the results obtained for K WCPQ. Finally, Section 6.6 focuses on two relevant K WCPQ variants, K WCPQ-First and K WSCPQ.

6.1. Experimental framework

We have carried out our experiments using four real-world datasets: *LAKES* (L) contains boundaries of water areas; *PARKS* (P) contains boundaries of parks or green areas; *ROADS* (R) includes roads and streets; and *BUILDINGS* (B) contains boundaries of buildings. The datasets we used contain OpenStreetMap public geographic information made available by the SpatialHadoop group² [14]. Note that the source datasets store complex features such as polygons (L, P, B) or line-strings (R). Note also that they represent the whole world, but the spatial features they contain appear only in land regions. Because of this, they represent a challenging scenario due to the irregular distribution of the features.

²Available at <http://spatialhadoop.cs.umn.edu/datasets.html>

Table 3: Statistics of the source datasets and generated point datasets.

Name	Source dataset		Generated dataset	
	#Features (M)	Size (GiB)	#Points (M)	Size (GiB)
BUILDINGS (B)	115	26	614	14.7
LAKES (L)	8.0	8.6	327	8.2
PARKS (P)	9.5	9.3	305	7.5
ROADS (R)	72	24	678	16.7

We preprocess each source dataset to generate a 2D point set from it. First, we extract all the vertices from the original geometries, and we round the coordinates of each vertex to 6 decimal places (this corresponds to a precision of approximately 10 centimeters). This rounding is necessary to map points to a discrete grid and eventually to k^2 -tree coordinates. We also apply a final preprocessing step that removes duplicate points (i.e., points that appear in multiple datasets with the exact same coordinates), ensuring that each point is unique across all datasets³. After these preprocessing steps, we obtain 2D point datasets that are stored in plain as (*longitude, latitude*) pairs.

Table 3 displays the number of spatial features and the original size of each source dataset, as well as the number of points generated from each of them after preprocessing. Note that the number of points is much higher than the number of original records, since we extract multiple points from each source feature.

Most of our experimental evaluation focuses on comparing our algorithms with the different plane-sweep variants introduced in Section 3.1, both for *KCPQ* and for ϵ DJQ. Table 4 describes the main plane-sweep alternatives used in our experiments. We use our own implementation of these algorithms, written in C++. For *KCPQ*, we have also performed a limited comparison with the implementation proposed in [35]. These experiments are described in Section 6.3.

Our experimental evaluation focuses on two main metrics: the space required by the representation, since the k^2 -tree representation is expected to compress the data efficiently, and the execution time of the different join queries to test the performance of the algorithms. Space requirements are measured statically, comparing the size of the k^2 -tree data structure and the size of the plain representation.

³This guarantees that the algorithms are tested in a challenging and realistic scenario in which two datasets are unlikely to have points at the exact same coordinates. Note that once a distance of 0 is found, filtering becomes trivial.

Table 4: Summary of the plane-sweep algorithms used.

Name	Description
PS-CS	Classic Plane-Sweep with Sliding Strip
PS-CC	Classic Plane-Sweep with Sliding Semi-Circle
PS-RRS	Reverse-Run Plane-Sweep with Sliding Strip
PS-RRC	Reverse-Run Plane-Sweep with Sliding Semi-Circle

Table 5: Summary of parameters used.

Parameter	Values
K for $KCPQ$	1, 10, 10^2 , 10^3 , 10^4 , 10^5
K for $KWCPQ$, $KWSCPQ$	1, 10, 10^2 , 10^3 , 10^4
ε ($\times 10^{-5}$)	7.5, 10, 25, 50, 75, 100
S for $KWCPQ$, $KWSCPQ$ (*)	45 (3.1%), 60 (5.6%), 90 (12.5%), 105 (17.0%), 120 (22.2%)
*: S represents the size of the square windows, in degrees. Values in parentheses represent the percentage of the space covered by the $S \times S$ window.	

Note that the input size is the main component of memory usage in most queries, but some join queries that return a very high number of results could require much more memory to store the uncompressed result set. Regarding query times, we measure the elapsed time for all techniques. Note that we only consider the time necessary to run the query itself, disregarding the time to load the files in memory, as well as the time to sort the input in the plane-sweep algorithms. To measure the scalability of our algorithms, we consider a number of parameters in each experiment. These parameters are summarized in Table 5 and described in detail in the following subsections.

All experiments were executed on an HP ProLiant DL380p Gen8 server, with two 6-core Intel® Xeon® CPU E5-2643 v2 @ 3.50GHz processors and 256GiB RAM (registered @1600 MHz). The operating system is Oracle Linux Server 7.9, with kernel Linux 4.14.35 (64bits). All algorithms were coded in C++ and are publicly available⁴. The k^2 -tree algorithms use the k^2 -tree implementation of SDSL-Lite⁵.

6.2. Construction of k^2 -trees and space requirements

We build a k^2 -tree for each dataset, using the simplest variant of k^2 -tree that uses plain bitmaps and $k = 2$ at all levels of the tree. Since the datasets contain

⁴Available at <https://gitlab.lbd.org.es/public-sources/djq/k2tree-djq>

⁵Available at <https://github.com/simongog/sdsl-lite>

Table 6: Space required by k^2 -tree representations.

Dataset	Plain (GiB)	Binary (GiB)	k^2 -tree (GiB)	Comp. ratio
BUILDINGS (B)	14.7	4.6	2.3	0.49
LAKES (L)	8.2	2.4	1.7	0.66
PARKS (P)	7.5	2.3	1.6	0.68
ROADS (R)	16.7	5.5	3.5	0.49

coordinates in degrees, with six decimal places, each k^2 -tree is built for a matrix with 180 million rows and 360 million columns. Point coordinates ($long, lat$) are translated to non-negative integer values that can be used as matrix coordinates (r, c), using the following formula: $(r, c) = ((lat + 90) \cdot 10^6, (long + 180) \cdot 10^6)$.

Table 6 displays the size of each dataset, the space required by its k^2 -tree representation, and the corresponding compression ratio. We display the size of the dataset stored in plain text, as well as the *binary size* if each coordinate is represented using two 32-bit words. The *compression ratio* is the ratio between the k^2 -tree and the binary input size. The k^2 -tree can reduce the required space to less than 50% of the binary size in the largest datasets and still obtain good compression in the smallest datasets. Note that our k^2 -trees do not include any optimization to improve compression.

6.3. Comparison with existing alternatives based on k^2 -trees

In this section, we compare our alternative with the previous work proposed in [35]. Their approach is also based on k^2 -trees and solves KCPQ with an algorithm similar to ours, but it does not solve ϵ DJQ or the constrained variants explored in our algorithms. Furthermore, their implementation has several limitations that make a fair comparison with our work impossible. The most important of these limitations is their inability to handle large matrices. Additionally, their implementation lacks some low-level optimizations built into ours, and their code is written in Java, while ours is written in C++.

Our experiments for this comparison use the same real-world datasets proposed in [35]: points extracted from roads and rivers in California (roads and rivers, containing 4499454 and 196902 points, respectively) and points extracted from car accidents and establishments with liquor licenses in Victoria, Australia (accidents and liquor-licenses, containing 76451 and 20480 points, respectively). These sets of points are mapped to a matrix of size 65536×65536 , replicating the original experiments. As stated above, using larger matrices was not possible due to the memory requirements of their implementation. Additionally, we have

Figure 3: Query times for $KCPQ$ in our implementation using k^2 -trees and ALBA- $KCPQ$, changing K .

preprocessed their California datasets to remove points that are shared between both datasets to generate our own roads-nodup and rivers-nodup.

This section focuses on query times, since their k^2 -tree should have very similar memory requirements to ours. However, their actual implementation requires much more memory than is needed to build the k^2 -trees. For each pair of datasets, we run $KCPQ$ for $K \in \{1, 10, 10^2, 10^3, 10^4, 10^5\}$. In this section, we run all queries for each pair of datasets in a single execution, starting with higher values of K . This *warm* execution has little effect on the query times of our implementation, but is very beneficial for ALBA- $KCPQ$, which is up to 100 times slower when each $KCPQ$ is executed separately, especially for $K = 1$.

Figure 3 shows a sample of the results obtained for $KCPQ$, comparing our work with ALBA- $KCPQ$. The two top charts represent the same experiments carried out in [35]: points on roads close to rivers and crashes close to establishments with liquor licenses. The bottom-left chart involves points on roads close to rivers, but with our preprocessed datasets that do not contain shared points. The bottom-right chart shows the join of rivers and liquor-licenses. All charts except the top-left one

show that our proposal is 2-5 times faster than ALBA-KCPQ. Note that although the full results are not displayed here for brevity, we have performed all possible pairwise joins with these datasets. The results in all cases are consistent with that trend: our proposal is generally 2-3 times faster than ALBA-KCPQ for any combination of datasets and the tested values of K .

Now, let us focus on the results in the top-left chart of Figure 3. Our proposal is faster for higher values of K , but slower for small values of K . This is mainly due to the high number of points shared by both datasets, which makes the KCPQ query abnormally simple (notice that the query times for rivers VS roads with small K become 10 times faster than any other join, even though this query involves the two largest datasets). As the number of points in common increases, KCPQ becomes simpler, to the point of degenerating into an intersection query when the number of points in common is greater than K . We argue that by removing the shared points, we can better reflect the actual performance of the KCPQ algorithms in challenging scenarios. To measure the effects of these duplicate points, we compare the results of the top-left and bottom-left charts of Figure 3. Recall that they involve the same source datasets, but the bottom-left chart uses the preprocessed roads-nodup and rivers-nodup datasets, in which common points are removed. The bottom-left chart shows much higher query times (both for our algorithms and ALBA-KCPQ) due to the higher complexity of the query. The comparison also shows a difference in the relative performance of each implementation: Our proposal becomes up to 5 times faster than ALBA-KCPQ when duplicates are removed and is significantly faster for smaller values of K . This is consistent with the results for any other pair of datasets and suggests that our algorithm is generally faster.

6.4. Query performance: KCPQ and ϵ DJQ

In this section, we compare the performance of k^2 -trees and plane-sweep algorithms for KCPQ and ϵ DJQ, two well-known distance-based join queries.

First, we compare our KCPQ algorithm with the four different baseline implementations defined in Table 4: PS-CS, PS-CC, PS-RRS, and PS-RRC. For these experiments, we test all possible pairwise combinations of our datasets and run the KCPQ algorithm for varying $K \in \{1, 10, 10^2, 10^3, 10^4, 10^5\}$.

Figure 4 displays the query times obtained by our algorithm and the four variants of plane-sweep. Note that a logarithmic scale is used in both axes. For smaller values of K , the k^2 -tree-based algorithm is the fastest in most cases. In most instances, k^2 -trees are 2–5 times faster than the fastest plane-sweep variant for $K \in \{1, 10, 100\}$. Among the plane-sweep variants, PS-RRS is usually the fastest technique for small K , and PS-CC becomes faster for higher K . However,

Figure 4: Query times for $KCPQ$ in k^2 -trees and plane-sweep variants, changing K .

the differences between PS-RRS and PS-RRC are very small, in general, so all variants except PS-CC are roughly equivalent for comparison with k^2 -trees.

The different join queries in Figure 4 yield very different query times, mainly due to the different sizes of the datasets. This difference becomes more evident for higher values of K . Nevertheless, in most joins, k^2 -trees are faster for all the values of K tested, and in some of them, their advantage against the plane-sweep variants even increases for higher values of K . These results confirm that an indexed solution based on k^2 -trees can outperform plane-sweep alternatives in most cases. The best-first traversal used in our algorithm is efficient thanks to the simplicity of tree traversal, based on low-level access and *rank* operations over the underlying bitmaps T and L . Additionally, the quadtree-like space partition used in k^2 -trees that separates the space in disjoint regions has been shown to be superior to other partitioning schemes in similar scenarios [34, 23]. The only exception in which k^2 -trees are the slowest solution for $K = 10^5$ is LxP and its inverse, corresponding to the join of the two smallest datasets.

Next, we focus on ε DJQ. We compare the k^2 -tree algorithm with only two plane-sweep variants: *Classic* plane-sweep with Sliding Strip (ε DJQ-CS) and *Reverse-Run* with Sliding Semi-Circle (ε DJQ-RRC). In the following experiments, we only display results for a subset of all possible joins of our datasets. We choose the following joins as representative subsets: LxB, LxP, PxR, and PxB. Note that these joins include LxP and PxR, which achieved the worst performance of k^2 -trees. We evaluate the performance of all algorithms for varying $\varepsilon \in (7.5, 10, 25, 50, 75, 100) \times 10^{-5}$ degrees. Note that the k^2 -tree implementation uses a resolution of 10^{-6} degrees, so when testing k^2 -trees we scale ε accordingly.

Figure 5 displays the results obtained for each join query. Our algorithm based on k^2 -trees is faster than the plane-sweep variants in all cases by a large factor (notice the logarithmic scale for query times). Both plane-sweep implementations behave similarly in all datasets, with differences in query times well below 10% in most cases. Noticeably, k^2 -tree-based algorithms are faster especially for smaller values of ε , which allows us to take advantage of the fast indexing capabilities of the k^2 -tree. These are the most relevant scenarios for this query since higher values of ε lead to an explosion in the number of results. For instance, for $\varepsilon = 100 \times 10^{-5}$ queries, return over 10^9 results and the storage of these results would become the main factor of memory used by both the k^2 -tree and the plane-sweep algorithms. Note that in our experiments, we measure the time to retrieve and count the query results, but we do not store them in RAM to avoid memory issues in some instances.

Figure 5: Query times for ϵ DJQ in k^2 -trees and plane-sweep variants, changing ϵ .

6.5. Constrained KCPQ: KWCPQ

We compare next the performance of KWCPQ, in order to analyze the effect of the window size and location on the performance of the algorithm. To do this, we generate square windows of different sizes, centered, and test the algorithms for different combinations of datasets.

Note that for all constrained KCPQ variants, we display results for *range query followed by plane-sweep* algorithms. As described in Section 5.1, these involve building a copy of the data corresponding to the query window and then performing a query on this subset of data, which requires additional resources. Simpler plane-sweep algorithms could be used, which work with full datasets and use constraints to only traverse and report points within the query window. However, the performance of these algorithms is unpredictable since they have a severe dependency on the distribution of the data and can easily degenerate into a brute-force search of the full datasets.

Figure 6 displays the results for k^2 -trees and the PS-CC and PS-RRC implementations of KWCPQ. We use square windows of different sizes, ranging from about 3% to 25% of the total space. Given that our datasets represent worldwide data, this corresponds to sizes $S \in \{45, 60, 90, 105, 120\}$, where S represents the side of a square window in degrees (i.e., $S = 45$ represents a query window of 45×45 degrees, covering roughly 3% of the total space).

As shown in Figure 6, k^2 -trees tend to be much more efficient than plane-sweep algorithms for larger query windows. Recall that the plane-sweep algorithm is based on the *window query followed by plane-sweep* technique: a window query is first performed on each dataset (additional memory resources are needed to store all points inside the window for each dataset), and then a plane-sweep algorithm is executed. In these cases, k^2 -trees are up to 4 times faster, and faster or at least competitive in all datasets. However, for smaller windows, the plane-sweep algorithm becomes faster than k^2 -trees in all datasets. As expected, the Reverse-Run variant is faster than the Classic plane-sweep in most instances.

Figure 7 displays the evolution of the query times as K changes for a fixed window size in all datasets. Results are very similar to those obtained for KCPQ queries: query times are relatively stable for small values of K , but as K increases, query times also increase significantly in all datasets, both using k^2 -trees and plane-sweep. Note that the results of Figures 6 and 7 only cover a subset of combinations for values of K and window sizes. Other combinations of parameters are omitted for brevity but follow similar trends.

In many real-world datasets, the location of the query window may be as relevant as its size. In previous experiments, we selected windows centered on

Figure 6: Query times for KWCPQ in k^2 -trees and plane-sweep variants, changing the size of the window. Fixed $K = 100$.

Figure 7: Query times for $KWCPQ$ in k^2 -trees and plane-sweep variants, changing K . Square window: $(-45, -45) - (45, 45)$.

Figure 8: Test points used in our experiments.

Figure 9: Query times obtained for $KWCPQ$ changing the center point of the query window (points location shown in Figure 8), for $K = 100$ and window of size $90^\circ \times 90^\circ$.

the map, but we conducted the same experimental evaluation with query windows centered on five other locations. Figure 8 displays the center points used for the windows (point 1 is the point used in previous experiments, and points 2–6 correspond to the additional 5 locations). Figure 9 displays the query times obtained for each point for fixed values of $K = 100$ and a fixed $S = 90$ (12.5% of the space). Results show that the location of the window has a considerable effect on query times (notice the log scale on the y-axis). The k^2 -tree algorithm is relatively stable, but query times may be twice as slow depending on the location of the query window. On the other hand, the plane-sweep algorithms are severely affected by the distribution of the data and may be up to 20 times slower for queries centered on point 6 than for queries centered on point 3. The higher variability obtained by plane-sweep techniques is expected, since these algorithms are very sensitive to the data distribution inside the query window during query processing. If a high concentration of points from the two datasets is found quickly, the value of the pruning distance can become smaller, making the pruning very aggressive and speeding up execution. On the other hand, if the pruning distance is not reduced swiftly, the algorithms become slower. In our scenario, a significant fraction of the query time variability may be due just to the number of points inside the query window, but the distribution of the points can also have significant effects on query times.

6.6. KWCPQ variants

We have also tested two significant variants of KWCPQ:

- KWCPQ-First is a variant that applies the window constraint only to the first dataset in the join.
- KWSCPQ implements the *semi-closest points* restricted to a query window and has been described in Section 5.2.

The first variant tested, KWCPQ-First, is a straightforward adaptation of our basic KWCPQ algorithm in k^2 -trees. We have performed the same experimental evaluation described for KWCPQ (joins LxB, LxP, PxR, and RxB, with 6 different origin points for windows, varying $K \in \{1, 10, 10^2, 10^3, 10^4\}$ and $S \in \{45, 60, 90, 105, 120\}$). We have compared k^2 -trees and the Classic plane-sweep with the Sliding Semi-Circle (PS-CC) and the corresponding Reverse-Run implementation (PS-RRC).

The overall results of our experiments show that KWCPQ-First yields very similar results to the basic KWCPQ, so for the sake of brevity, we will omit detailed results for this variant. Indeed, the query times in k^2 -trees for a KWCPQ-First query are consistently between 80% and 139% of the times obtained for the KWCPQ query with the same configuration, with an average ratio around 1.03 (i.e., KWCPQ-First is 3% slower than KWCPQ) and a standard deviation around 0.06. Plane-sweep algorithms also yield overall similar query times for KWCPQ-First to those of KWCPQ, but they are more unpredictable. KWCPQ-First is, on average, 7% slower than KWCPQ, but in a few queries, it becomes several orders of magnitude slower. Ignoring just 5 outlier queries (of 750 conducted), the average query times of KWCPQ-First are again almost identical to those of KWCPQ (ratio of 1.002, with a standard deviation of 0.08). These results show that both operations are, in practice, very similar, and also highlight the inherent variability of plane-sweep algorithms that may yield significantly different query times to apparently similar queries, depending on the actual distribution of the points. Overall, regarding KWCPQ-First, the same conclusions found for KWCPQ hold: k^2 -trees are more consistent than plane-sweep variants and are faster on average for larger windows, especially for smaller values of K .

Next, we tackle the KWSCPQ variant that imposes a major change in the algorithms and leads to potentially more costly calculations, both in k^2 -trees and the plane-sweep variants. We conducted the same set of experiments for this query as for KWCPQ (joins LxB, LxP, PxR, and RxB; square windows centered at 6 different points; varying $K \in \{1, 10, 10^2, 10^3, 10^4\}$; and varying $S \in \{45, 60, 90, 105, 120\}$

Figure 10: Query times for $KWSCPQ$, centered windows with $S = 90$ degrees, varying K .

degrees). We compared k^2 -trees with PS-CC and PS-RRC, but we only display results for PS-RRC since it is faster overall and produces more stable query times.

In most instances, the results for $KWSCPQ$ are similar to those obtained for previous operations. Globally, k^2 -trees are around 5% slower in $KWSCPQ$ than in $KWCPQ$. On the other hand, PS-RRC is, on average, 3 times slower in $KWSCPQ$ than in $KWCPQ$, but the difference is considerable in some scenarios: with large values of K ($K \in \{10^3, 10^4\}$), and in smaller windows ($S \in \{45, 60\}$, around 3–5% of the total space). In these instances, PS-RRC is up to 100 times slower to answer $KWSCPQ$ than to answer the equivalent $KWCPQ$ query. Nevertheless, for larger windows and smaller values of K , k^2 -trees and PS-RRC have similar query times (within 20% of each other) to answer $KWCPQ$, $KWCPQ$ -First and $KWSCPQ$ queries for the same configuration. Therefore, the conclusions for $KWCPQ$ still hold for these cases. The remainder of this section focuses on the effect of larger K and smaller windows.

Figure 10 shows the evolution of query times as K evolves, with $S = 90$, for all datasets. The results are similar to those obtained for other $KWCPQ$ operations, with k^2 -trees being more competitive for smaller K . For the larger values of K , k^2 -trees are now competitive in more datasets: they are still much faster in LxB and obtain similar times in LxP and PxR. In RxB, k^2 -trees are slower for large K but always within a factor of 1.4–2.

Figure 11: Query times for $KWSCPQ$, fixed $K = 100$, varying S .

Figure 11 displays the evolution of the query times as S evolves for fixed $K = 100$ in all datasets. The behavior of the k^2 -trees is consistent in all datasets, as in previous experiments, showing a smooth evolution of query times. On the other hand, PS-RRC is more variable, reaching, in some cases, good query times in large windows but also obtaining poor query times in small windows. For example, in LxP and RxB, the k^2 -tree algorithm is much faster for small windows, whereas in LxB, the query times obtained by both techniques are similar. However, for larger windows, PS-RRC becomes relatively faster, achieving query times comparable to or faster than those of k^2 -trees. Notice, however, that the plane-sweep algorithms need to make a copy of the points within the query window to answer queries efficiently, since working with the full dataset causes poor performance and a much higher dependency on the distribution of the points. Therefore, for these large windows, PS-RRC becomes faster at the cost of much higher memory requirements due to the load in memory of the uncompressed data and the additional copy for the points in the query window when the *range query followed by plane-sweep* technique is applied.

7. Conclusions and Future Work

This work presents a family of algorithms to solve common DJQs over point datasets stored using k^2 -trees, a compact data structure based on quadtree space partitioning that takes advantage of bitmaps to compactly represent and query the data efficiently. We propose algorithms that efficiently answer K CPQ and ϵ DJQ queries, as well as variants like K WCPQ and K WSCPQ. These algorithms take advantage of the indexing capabilities of the k^2 -tree, which divides the space into disjoint regions following a quadtree-like decomposition, and use distance metrics that are easier to compute due to the fixed-size partition of the space. Our algorithms also take advantage of low-level operations on the bitmaps T and L to efficiently traverse the k^2 -tree following a best-first traversal of the conceptual tree.

Our experimental evaluation using large real-world datasets shows that our algorithms are competitive with alternatives based on plane-sweep techniques in most cases. We are faster than the alternatives to answer K CPQ in most scenarios and much faster to answer ϵ DJQ. Experiments with window-constrained variants K WCPQ and K WSCPQ also show that the k^2 -tree algorithms are faster for relatively large query windows, especially for values of K that are not too high, the most common scenario for these queries. Additionally, our results show that our algorithms based on k^2 -trees are less affected by the location of the query window and, hence, the distribution of the data, making our query times more predictable than those of plane-sweep-based algorithms. This query performance is combined with reduced space requirements due to the compression achieved by k^2 -trees.

The algorithms we propose take advantage of the internal structure of the k^2 -tree and can be adapted to work with k^2 -tree variants that achieve even better compression [8] in datasets with high clustering of points. Additionally, the algorithms follow the fixed space partitioning of the k^2 -tree, so we plan to explore their potential in Spark-based distributed systems that could take advantage of the lower space requirements of the k^2 -trees.

We also plan to explore the potential of k^2 -tree-based algorithms in other common DJQs. All algorithms proposed in this work share a coherent basis, to the extent that variants like K WCPQ that require significant changes to the plane-sweep algorithms are handled with minor checks in our algorithms, and we believe that other operations such as K NN Join Queries could also be managed efficiently using similar ideas.

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